

Effect of Principal's Emotional Intelligence Management on Principal's Leadership Quality: A Literature Review

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ABSTRACT: Emotional intelligence management skills offer leadership qualities that are sufficient to advance an organization and to achieve its goals. Therefore, the skills to manage emotional intelligence must be possessed by a leader, including principal. The importance of emotional intelligence management for principal's leadership attracts researchers to do a literature review study. There are several articles that discuss the principal's emotional intelligence management. The purpose of this literature review is to determine the effect of emotional intelligence management on the quality of school principal's leadership in the world. Based on the results of literature reviews from various countries in the world, most of the studies show that emotional intelligence management has a positive and significant influence on the quality of principal's leadership.

KEYWORDS: Emotional intelligence, Emotional intelligence management, Leadership, Principal leadership

1. INTRODUCTION

Management is a process of activities that starts with planning the program of activities and continues with implementing program activities, empowering resources (natural resources and human resources), and evaluating activities both short and long term. (Munawarah, Yusrizal, & Usman, 2020). Management and leadership are very important in social life, especially in educational organizations, and staff job satisfaction is one of the most important problems in management. (Saeed et al., 2012). It is not easy for organizations to adapt to changing times. In the management approach, employee knowledge and skills and emotions are very important. In addition to managing staff performance, managers must also be able to manage staff emotions. Because the goals of educational organizations are realized by people, not by machines (Güngör & Helvaci, 2020)

In every organization, leaders are required to have the ability to direct or coordinate their members to achieve organizational goals. A leader is a person who chooses, complements, trains, and influences one or more followers who have various talents, abilities, and skills and focuses their behavior on the mission and goals of the organization, which makes followers voluntarily and enthusiastically exert spiritual, emotional, and their physical energy, in a coordinated effort to achieve the mission and goals of the organization (Gandolfi & Stone, 2018). The organization must have a leader, for schools, the leader refers to the principal. Leaders are always directed to organize and coordinate the work of teachers and other workers in the school, in order to achieve school goals (Nyenembe, Maslowski, Nimrod, & Peter, 2016). According to Thomas Carlyle (1847), in 'the great man theory', leaders are born as people who are endowed with heroic potential who are able to become leaders (Nawaz & Khan_ 2016).

Besides, leaders must also have good emotional intelligence that can be a role model for their followers. The term 'emotional intelligence' was created by Peter Salovey and John Mayer in 1990 (Mayer, Roberts, & Barsade, 2008). They say that there are four components in the emotional intelligence model, namely, the ability to understand the emotions, use the emotions to facilitate thinking, understand and manage the emotions, and combine those skills to form an intelligence based on intelligence theory and definition. In 1995, Goleman popularized the concept of emotional intelligence which described five skills related to emotional intelligence: self-motivation, self-regulation, self-awareness, social skills (relationship management) and social awareness (empathy) (Dippenaar & Schaap, 2017). Furthermore, in 1990 Salovey and Mayer defined emotional intelligence as "the ability to monitor feelings and emotions of someone and those of others, to distinguish between them and use this information to guide one's thoughts and actions". They suggest that emotional intelligence is more easily recognized than academic intelligence (Mandell & Pherwani, 2003).

The concept of emotional intelligence is based in the context of intelligence theory. The pure theory of emotional intelligence integrates key ideas of intelligence and emotion. From intelligence theory, the idea that intelligence involves the ability to do abstract reasoning began to emerge. They stated that emotional intelligence consists of the ability to understand, respond, manipulate, and manage emotional information without experiencing it (Ugoani & Amu, 2015).

In his research, Joseph (1998) found that while IQ scores have no predictive value (correlation of 0.07 with performance), EQ scores predict 27% of job performance. Leaders are judged on their ability to handle themselves and the team. A leader with vision and enthusiasm can achieve great things by giving enthusiasm and energy to his team members. Today, leaders are expected to guide, motivate, inspire, listen, persuade, and create meaning. Therefore, dealing with emotions is an important part of a leader's success (Mathew & Gupta, 2015).

Another benefit of Emotional Intelligence is that it allows us to distance ourselves from negative emotions, so that we can work at a higher level. Goleman argues about "mixed model", which has 5 main components: self-awareness, self-regulation, social skills, empathy, and motivation (Savel & Munro, 2016).

From the explanation of Emotional Intelligence above, we can understand that Emotional Intelligence is very important for a leader, so that a leader should be able to manage his emotions well. Effective leaders have emotional intelligence, which is the ability to recognize and manage emotions in a person and others. A leader's emotional intelligence influences his ability in managing an organization. Based on the description above, it is necessary to investigate "How Do Principals in Manage Their Emotional Intelligence?".

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Emotional Intelligence Management

The ability to manage emotions is one of the competencies needed by people to face the Fourth Industrial Revolution (4.0) (Arifin, 2019). Emotional intelligence according to Ilyas is the ability to understand themselves and others, so they can put themselves in others' situations and can also control themselves. That ability makes them able to manage every action and reaction that is controlled by: (1) self-control, (2) enthusiasm, (3) perseverance, (4) personality and kindness that lead to success in daily life or at the workplace (Ilyas & Abdullah, 2016). Then, they can apply their skills to manage work. This shows that emotional intelligence has a positive effect on performance. According to Ginanjar, emotional intelligence is a set of skills and competencies when cognitive abilities do not affect one's ability to succeed in doing tasks. Salovey and Mayer (1990) define emotional intelligence as "the ability to monitor feelings and emotions of a person and others". To recognize the difference between themselves and use this information to guide their own thoughts and actions (Mandell & Pherwani, 2003).

Emotional intelligence consists of core skills and high-level skills. Core skills include knowing yourself, maintaining a conversation, understanding others accurately, and communicating flexibly. Otherwise, high-level skills include: taking bold responses, generating choices, embracing vision, having courage, and showing determination. The combination of core skills and higher order can often lead to effective leadership, perhaps because it shows an awareness of the needs of others and the ability to respond effectively to various situations (Hayashi & Ewert, 2006).

Salovey and Mayer (1990) coined the term "emotional intelligence" (EI) based on their study of the interaction between emotions and thoughts. Another study conducted by Gardner in 1996, included two types of EI in the theory of seven multiple intelligences. In 1995, the Emotional Intelligence theory revealed by Daniel Golemans further acted as a catalyst for discussion in explaining why EI, measured by emotional quotient (EQ), can show personal success in life (Butler & Chinowsky, 2006).

Goleman's EQ model has categorized emotional intelligence into five factors of emotional intelligence: self-awareness, self-regulation, self-motivation, empathy and social skills. This model has been further developed by identifying several existing domains (Harun, Ishak, Yusoff, & Amat, 2017). Emotional intelligence becomes important for leaders with the support of findings that emotional intelligence is superior to intellectual intelligence, because cognitive resources (emotions, motivations and desires) are needed as problem solving input (Bashir, 2017).

Principal

The principal is a leader who has an important role in developing educational institutions, as the holder of control in educational institutions. In this case, the role of the principal must be maximized by his role in improving the quality of education, as a manager,

so that it can influence the staff and teachers, both directly and indirectly. Di samping itu, kepala sekolah juga mempunyai peranan yang sangat besar dalam mengembangkan kualitas pendidikan di lembaga pendidikan tersebut (Rosyadi & Pardjono, 2015). Principals play a very important role in school leadership under the Main Responsibility System that their performance is definitely monitored by education (Feng, 2020). The principal is the key driver for school development and progress and is responsible for increasing accountability for student success and programs. To achieve this goal, the principal's leadership needs to be empowered, so that the principal is able to play in accordance with the duties, authority, and responsibilities. The principal must be good at leading groups and managing delegation of tasks and authority (Fitrah, 2017)

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research can be categorized as literature review. The purpose of this review literature is to get a theoretical foundation that can support solving a problem. The review process starts with a search engine, google scholar, to search for articles by keywords: "Principal Emotional Intelligence Management". The search ranged from articles published in 2003-2020, and identified 200 studies and articles related to these keywords. Article criteria that can be used as literature in this study are:

- a. Qualitative results from 'Principal Emotional Intelligence Management'
- b. Research from various countries in the world
- c. The research article is written in English
- d. Dissertations and theses are excluded

The steps in the Literature Review of each variable in 'Principal Emotional Intelligence Management' are:

Step 1: Formulate the Problem

- Choose a topic that fits the issue
- The problem must be written completely and accurately

Step 2: Search for the Literatures

- Search for the literature relevant to the research
- Get an overview of the research topic
- Research sources will be very helpful if supported by knowledge related to the topic being studied.
- The sources must provide an overview / summary related to previous research.

Step 3: Data evaluation

- Pay attention to the contributions made by articles to the topic
- Pay attention to contributions from articles related to the topic
- Data can be in the form of quantitative data, qualitative data or a combination of both

Step 4: Analysis and Interpretation

Discuss and summarize the literature

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Principal's Emotional Intelligence Management

This section discusses the main findings of this study, which are reviewed from several articles. The analysis shows that most of the articles focus on "How Do Principals in the World Manage Their Emotional Intelligence?". The articles reviewed in this study are research articles conducted in various countries in the world. Table 1 explains the results of the literature review.

Table I Principals' Emotional Intelligence Management

Author and Year of Publication	Title	Country	Methods	Sample	Results
Munawarah, Yusrizal and Usman (2020)	Principal Management in Improving the Educational Quality at Elementary School	Indonesia	Qualitative	-----	Based on this research, principals must prepare themselves to build leadership quality in line

	Cluster of Bungong Keupula, Indonesia				with the vision of the school, the quality includes: the quality of the curriculum, the quality of teaching, the improvement of teacher quality and performance, continuing education for teachers, and so on.
Saeid and Farahbakhsh (2012)	The role of emotional intelligence in increasing quality of work life in school principals	Iran	Qualitative	139 principals	This research reveals that emotional intelligence can have a good influence on the work environment of the principal. With a good ability in managing emotional intelligence, will build a better atmosphere for the school principal. And for this reason, the quality of the principal's performance has improved very well.
Gungor and Helvaci (2020)	The Relationship between the emotion management pr oficiencies of school administrators and the motivation level of the teachers	Turkey	Quantitative	374 teachers	This research proves that there is a strong and positive correlation between emotional management and teacher's motivation.
Gandolfi and Stone (2018)	Leadership, Leadership Styles, and Servant Leadership	Malaysia	Qualitative	-----	This study found that servant leadership met the criteria for effective leadership
Nyenyembe1, Maslowski, Nimrod, Levina and Peter (2016)	Leadership Styles and Teachers' Job Satisfaction in Tanzanian Public Secondary Schools	Tanzania	Qualitative	180 Teachers	In this article, researchers revealed that teachers were more satisfied with their work when the principal worked closely with them (the principal was involved) by guiding them and paying attention to their personal well-being.

Zakeer Ahmed and Nawaz Irfanullah (2016)	Leadership Theories and Styles: A Literature Review	Pakistan	Qualitative	-----	The finding of this research advises principals that to achieve effective leadership, transformational leaders must focus their energy on the vision and long-term goals of the school, align and change the system, and develop and train the labor (teachers and other staffs) in school.
Dippenaar and Pieter (2017)	The impact of coaching on the emotional and social intelligence competencies of leaders	South Africa	Mix method	30 leaders	This study revealed that training significantly affected the emotional and social intelligence competencies of leaders in terms of emotional intelligence
Mandell and Pherwani (2003)	Relationship Between Emotional Intelligence and Transformational Leadership Style A Gender comparison	United States	Hierarchical regression analysis	32 men	The findings of this study revealed that a significant predictive correlation ($p < 0.05$) was found between the transformation of rational leadership style and emotional intelligence.
John,Ugoani, Christain and Amu (2015)	Dimensions of Emotional Intelligence and Transformational Leadership: A Correlation Analysis	United States	Quantitative	47 Managers	This study stated that the Pearson correlation coefficient value revealed in this research article, shows the strong positive relationship between emotional intelligence and transformational leadership style
Mathew and Gupta (2015)	Transformational Leadership: Emotional Intelligence	India	Qualitative	300 Leaders	This research explains about the profile of transformational leaders who are smart in managing their feelings

					so that they can move their emotions to lead in the right direction.
Richard, Savel, Cindy, and Munro (2019)	Emotional Intelligence: For the Leader in US	United States	Quantitative	-----	The findings of this study confirm that one of the most important things to be considered by principals is that skills in managing Emotional Intelligence can be increased through training, effort, discipline, motivation, and continuous repetition.
Arifin (2019)	Management of Teachers' Emotional Intelligence in the Industrial Revolution 4.0 Era	Indonesia	Qualitative	-----	Based on this research: a) teachers can evaluate their strengths and limitations in recognizing and understanding school work procedures (self-awareness); b) teachers are able to manage their emotions and negative impulses when dealing with problems (self-management); c) teachers are able to show empathy and a desire to help others (social care); d) teachers are influenced by intrinsic motivation to become better individuals, work harder, believe in career development, and adapt to new environments (self motivation); e) teachers are able to maintain good relations with their supervisors, fellow teachers/staffs, students, and others.
Ilyas and Abdullah (2016)	The Effect of Leadership, Organizational Culture, Emotional Intelligence,	Indonesia		78 teachers	The findings of this study reveal that: 1. Leadership directly affects teacher

	and Job Satisfaction on Performance				performance; 2. Emotional quotes directly affect teacher performance; 3. Job Satisfaction directly affects teacher performance; 4. Leadership directly affects job satisfaction; 5. Organizational culture directly affectss job satisfaction; 6. Emotional Quotes directly affect job satisfaction.
Hayashi and Ewert (2006)	Outdoor Leaders' Emotional Intelligence and Transformational Leadership	USA	Qualitative	46 People	This research found that there is a moderate and positive correlation between emotional intelligence and transformational leadership
Colleen, Butler, Paul and Chinowsky (2006)	Emotional Intelligence and Leadership Behavior in Contruction Executives	Istanbul	Quantitative	130 Executives	This research states that the leaders have indeed proven that the strength of the relationship is not only measured by the relationship that is seen but also something strong as measured by social standards
Harun, Ishak, Yusoff and Amat (2017)	Emotional Intelligence and Leadership Pr ofiles among Students' Representative Council of Malaysia Public Universities	Malaysia	Quantitative	238 Members	The findings of this study state that leadership quality is shown from the acquisition of high scores in all factors (there are a total of seven factors) that are measured: Leadership Strategies and Models, Recruitment, Performance quality and respect from workers, Strategic Distribution, Developing, Engaging and Maintaining and Building HR capabilities.

					The overall score for leadership quality in Malaysia was found to be high.
Nadeem Ahmad Bashir (2017)	Leadership Connection to Emotional Intelligence and Stress at Workplace	Saudi Arabia	Qualitative	----	This research concluded that, emotional intelligence makes leaders qualified to deal with stressful situations, and general intelligence can be improved as soon as leaders cope with stress living environment.
Rosyadi and Pardjono (2015)	Roles of The Principal As A Manager In The Improvement of The Quality of Education At SMP 1 Cilawu, Garut Regency	Indonesia	Qualitative		This research shows that the principal's role as a manager is: 1. Planning the program by detailing the needs of teachers and staffs, planning the curriculum, planning a policy of adding two hours of counseling guidance subjects per week; 2. Creating an organizational structure that involves parents through the school committee and completes the necessary infrastructure; 3. Give a good and calm example at work, motivate and reward personnel (both morally and materially), improve welfare, include teachers and school staffs in training and education, and motivate senior teachers to have a spirit of life-long education; 4. Overseeing the learning output, learning process, and student development (starting from the

					admission process until students finish school).
Muh. Fitrah (2017)	Peran Kepala Sekolah Dalam Meningkatkan Mutu Pendidikan	Indonesia	Qualitative	-----	This research confirms that the principal’s job is not only to lead ceremonies and wait for incoming letters to be signed, but also to maintain and improve the quality of education in schools.

Based on the results of the analysis that researchers conclude from several articles, most of the main articles focus on how emotional intelligence management affects the leadership performance of principals. The articles used in this study come from various countries in the world. Based on these articles, the research method used in the preparation of this article is survey research with a qualitative approach. The survey method used is a survey used to explain relationships and test hypotheses. Data collection using a questionnaire, which has been entered and complete the score on each item. While the data analysis technique used to test the hypothesis is a simple linear data analysis technique and multiple correlations. Based on the results of research, interviews and observations.

Research on principal’s emotional intelligence management has been studied in various countries. Table 1 shows that the research has been studied in various educational institutions, including universities. The results of the majority of studies indicate that good emotional intelligence management can positively and significantly influence the principal’s leadership. This conclusion is supported by the statements of Saeid and Farakhbakhsh in their research “Emotional Intelligence is able to provide a better working environment for principals” (Farahbakhsh, 2012) . Marlene and Pieter’s research states that “training significantly influences leaders’ emotional and social intelligence competencies in terms of emotional intelligence” (Dippenaar & Schaap, 2017). Furthermore, the results of Nadeem’s research stated that “Emotional intelligence makes leaders qualified to deal with stressful situations” (Bashir, 2017). Therefore, it can be stated that emotional intelligence management influences the leadership of principals.

5. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the study, it can be concluded in general that when we consider all studies reviewed about the management of the emotional intelligence of principals conducted in various countries in the world, there is a significant correlation between these two variables (emotional intelligence and principal’s leadership). Emotional intelligence has a positive and significant influence on the principal’s leadership

Like research in general, this review also has limitations or weaknesses. First, the articles reviewed are only articles written in English, so, other articles in languages other than English are not reviewed due to language limitations. Second, dissertations and theses are not reviewed in this article because those can cause publication bias in the results. Third, the scope of the article reviewed is still very limited, and it is very difficult to get literature that combines the two variables appropriately. These limitations are opportunities for further research, in particular, how principal emotional intelligence influences principalship quality in an Indonesian school context.

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